

ANALYSIS OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING PROCESS WITH PROGRESSIVE RESIN INJECTION

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SUMMARY: In resin transfer molding, the increase of fiber volume fraction decelerates the resin flow. For a fast resin flow without increasing injection pressure, multiple injection ports are used. If all the injection ports are opened simultaneously, the resin front become very complicated and numerous weld lines and air bubbles may form. In this study, injection ports were opened in a sequential manner as the resin front advances. Mold filling process was simulated numerically using Control Volume Finite Element Method (CV-FEM). An optimized schedule for opening each resin injection port was obtained from numerical simulation. Experiments were performed following the proposed schedule. The resin front shapes observed from the experiments were compared with the numerical results. Close agreement was found. The progressive opening of the injection ports reduced the injection pressure as well as the injection time by a big margin.

KEYWORDS: resin transfer molding (RTM), progressive opening of multiple injection ports, mold filling simulation, visualized mold filling experiment

INTRODUCTION

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) is an effective method for the manufacturing of composite parts, especially for large and complex geometries. RTM is performed at low pressure and low temperature (typically below 5atm. and 100°C). As the process is performed at a low pressure, the mold can be made of light metals, or even of composites. The tooling cost for molds can be remarkably saved and the manufacturing cost may be also broken down by a big margin compared to other composite processes. Therefore, RTM is suitable for manufacturing composite parts with frequent model changes at a low capital investments. RTM is performed by injecting catalyzed thermoset resin through a gate into the mold cavity pre-loaded with porous fibrous reinforcement, which is called a preform. The impregnation of fiber preform with resin is performed by transferring resin through the micro pores within the fibrous texture until the mold is fully charged (see Figure 1). As the fiber carries most of the mechanical load, the increase of the volumetric fraction of fiber is crucial in enhancing the specific strength and modulus, and thus reducing the weight, of the product. In order to achieve the premium properties of RTM products, it is necessary to enhance the fiber volume fraction. As the fiber volume fraction increases, the size of the micro pores within fibrous texture is decreased and the permeability of preform is also decreased. Thus, high fiber volume fraction leads to a deceleration of the resin flow speed during the resin impregnation into the preform, subsequently increasing the manufacturing time. Higher injection pressure enables faster resin flow, but the preform may be deformed or washed out at excessively high injection pressure. As a result, mold filling in RTM gets difficult with increasing fiber volume

fraction, so RTM process becomes impractical to manufacture relatively large parts for fiber volume fraction over 40~50%.

In order to reduce the processing time, one of the widely used practice is to elevate the resin temperature by heating the mold. If the resin is heated, the viscosity decreases and thus the flow speed is enhanced. Due to the heat transfer from the mold to the thermoset, cure reaction take place during the mold filling. Since the cure reaction during mold filling advances the gelation of resin, the time required for the post-curing can be reduced. Hence, the heated mold reduces the total manufacturing time by accelerated curing as well as by reduced resin viscosity. However, if the resin temperature is raised excessively, the gelation of resin may be reached too fast and the resin flow may prematurely stop before completion of mold filling.

A more effective method for enhancing the flow is to use multiple injection gates. Each injection gate in a multi-gate system fills smaller area than was responsible for in a single gate system, and the time required for mold filling can be remarkably reduced. The problem in a multi-gate system is the entrapment of numerous air bubbles where the flow fronts from two or more gates merge together (see Figure 2a). In this study, the opening of the gates is progressively performed along a well-designed sequence, not simultaneously. Each injection gate in the present multi-gate system is automatically controlled to be opened at the exact moment when the flow front has just passed over the gate. Thus the flow front remains simple and the number of ventilation ports can be minimized (see Figure 2b). Another advantage from the progressive opening of multiple injection gates is that the flow front velocity can be regulated within a bounded range. The flow front slows down as it moves away from the injection gate, because the gradient of pressure decreases with increasing distance between the gate and the flow front. The flow front velocity can be restored by opening a new gate at the moment when the flow front passes over the gate as shown in Figure 3.

The mold filling simulation for resin transfer molding has been conducted using different numerical techniques. A number of investigations have been performed using finite difference method (FDM) using boundary fitted coordinate[1] and finite element method with moving grids[2]. In these techniques, the calculation meshes change every time step as the calculation domain changes. Even though the flow front can be traced precisely, regeneration of the meshes at each time step imposes a great amount of extra computational efforts. In order to circumvent the problem with mesh regeneration, control volume finite element method (CVFEM) [4,5] is widely used. In this numerical scheme, computation is relatively fast due to the fixed finite element mesh, while the exact location of the resin front is difficult to determine. Um and Lee [3] applied boundary element method (BEM) for two dimensional flat mold in which the permeability and the resin viscosity are constant.

The progressive opening of multiple injection gates in RTM has been previously practiced in the industrial manufacturing processes. Chan and Morgan[6] investigated the resin flow during mold filling with progressively opened multiple injection gates focused on the microscopic flow within fiber bundles for a simplified one dimensional rectangular flow.

In this study, control volume finite element method (CVFEM) was employed to simulate the flow of resin during mold filling. Especially, the effect of the progressive opening of the injection ports on the fill time was investigated both numerically and experimentally for realistic multidimensional geometries. In the experiment, sensors were developed to detect the arrival of resin front. The sensors were validated by comparing the detection signal with the observation of a visualized flow during mold filling.

MATHEMATICAL MODELING

Consider a mold with a thin cavity loaded with fibrous preform. The permeability of the preform may be anisotropic and nonuniform. The mold cavity is assumed as a three dimensional shell, as the thickness of the cavity is negligibly small compared to other dimensions. Resin is injected at a number of designed points. The mold is heated to facilitate the resin flow and the curing. The problem is to find out the resin front location, pressure, temperature and degree of cure distributions as functions of time.

The flow of the resin inside the mold through the fiber preform can be assumed to follow the Darcy's law given by

$$\vec{V} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where \vec{V} is the resin velocity, p is the pressure and μ is the resin viscosity. $[K]$ is the permeability tensor for anisotropic porous media and can be a function of location. The mass conservation requires

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Substituting Eq.(1) into Eq.(2) yields

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla p \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

The energy conservation equation is given by

$$\rho c \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_r c_r \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = k \nabla^2 T + \phi \dot{G} \quad (4)$$

where ρ , c and k are the density, specific heat and thermal conductivity, respectively. ϕ is the fiber volume fraction and the subscript r denote the resin. \dot{G} is the heat generation due to the curing reaction and is given by

$$\dot{G} = \Delta H \dot{m} \quad (5)$$

where ΔH is the heat of reaction and \dot{m} is the generation of mass of cured resin.

The conservation of the chemical species is given by

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\phi} \vec{V} \cdot \nabla \alpha = \dot{m} \quad (6)$$

where α is the degree of cure. \dot{m} is given by an empirical relation[7]

$$\dot{m} = (k_1 + k_2 \alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n \quad (7)$$

$$k_1 = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_1}{RT}\right), \quad k_2 = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right)$$

where m , n , A_1 , A_2 , E_1 , E_2 are constants which are determined from experimental data.

The boundary conditions for the above governing equations are given as

Flow Inlet:

$$P=P_0 \text{ or } V=V_0; \quad T=T_0; \quad \alpha=0$$

Solid Boundary:

$$\frac{dp}{dn} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Free Surface: $p = 0; q_{in} = (1 - \phi)\rho_f c_f V_n (T_f - T)$

where T_f represents the temperature of the fiber.

During and after mold filling, the resin undergoes an exothermic cure reaction after which the resin can be solidified.

Dusi et al [8] suggested a modification to the model of Kamal and Sorour[7] to account for that resin curing reaction cannot proceed beyond a certain level if the resin is exposed to a given temperature below a critical value. In this model, the isothermal degree of cure, β is defined similar to the degree of cure in Kamal and Sorour's model.

$$\frac{d\beta}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2\beta^m)(1 - \beta)^n \quad (9)$$

$$k_1 = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_1}{RT}\right), \quad k_2 = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_2}{RT}\right)$$

The actual degree of cure α is related to the isothermal degree of cure β as,

$$\alpha = \frac{H_T}{H_U} \beta \quad (10)$$

where H_T is the heat of reaction which can be liberated under a given temperature, while H_U is the total heat of reaction possibly generated when the temperature is sufficiently raised so that the resin is perfectly cured. The relation between H_T and H_U is again approximated as a piecewise linear function of temperature as,

$$\frac{H_T}{H_U} = C_1 \times T + C_2 \quad T < T_c \quad (11)$$

$$H_T = H_U \quad T \geq T_c$$

where C_1 , C_2 and T_c are the constants which can be experimentally obtained.

The viscosity of the resin can be modeled as follows as a function of temperature and degree of cure [9].

$$\mu = \mu_\infty \exp\left(\frac{\Delta E_\mu}{RT} + \kappa\alpha\right) \quad (12)$$

Here, μ_∞ , ΔE_μ and κ are constants which can be determined experimentally.

In order to optimize the design of the injection gates and opening time, numerical simulation is required for the resin flow during mold filling. The present mold filling problem has a moving boundary, continuously changing the shape at every time step. In order to solve the governing equations along with the boundary conditions, the control volume finite element method (CVFEM) is used in combination with the fixed grid method for the efficiency in solving the present moving boundary problem. By applying the control volume approach to the governing equations, a system of algebraic equations can be obtained. The detailed formulation process can be found elsewhere[10].

EXPERIMENTS

Experimental setup used in this study is shown in Figure 4. Lower mold plate was made of steel while upper plate was made of 30mm thick transparent Plexiglas. Location of the injection port was selected by inspection. The moving resin front was recorded using a video

camera located right above the mold. Oil was supplied from a cylindrical reservoir which was pressurized by compressed nitrogen. Pressure of the oil was measured using a pressure transducer installed right before the injection port. The pressure of the nitrogen gas was regulated to maintain a constant injection pressure. The viscosity of the oil was also measured using a rheometer (RMS). In order to detect the resin front passing over the individual injection gates, flow front sensors are required. Photo-sensors, made by assembling an infrared LED and a photo detector in a single package, were flush mounted near the injection gates to detect the flow front. The mechanism of the detection of the flow front is illustrated in Figure 5. The optical refractive index of resin is very similar to that of glass fiber, while the refractive index of the air is much different to that of fiber. Before the resin front arrives, the dry fiber preform scatter the infrared light emitted by the LED, and much of the emitted light will be refracted back to the sensor, to produce a high output voltage (see Figure 5a). When the resin front reaches the sensor, since the refractive indices of fiber and resin are quite similar, the infrared light emitted by the LED passes through the wet medium of resin-fiber mixture with little refraction, and the output voltage from the sensor by the refracted light is low (see Figure 5b). Figure 5c illustrates the output voltage from the sensor before and after the arrival of the resin front. A clear difference of no less than 2.0V was observed in the output voltage. In order to prevent a premature opening of the injection gates, the sensors were located at some distances downstream to the resin flow. Each injection gate was logically connected to their neighboring sensors except for the first injection gate which must be initially open with the start of mold filling. Three additional sensors were planted in order to verify the numerical prediction of the flow front location at more points. The locations of the injection gates and sensors are shown in Figure 6.

An experiment for the single gate injection has been performed at a constant pressure of 100kPa. The mold assembly was maintained at room temperature of 15°C. Engine oil (SAE 10W-30 from Honam Petroleum, Inc.) was used to imitate the resin in the experiments. The viscosity at the room temperature was 0.1569Pa·s. The fiber preform was made by stacking seven plies of chopped glass strand mats (LG Owens-Corning CM450-723). The fiber volume fraction was found to be 0.393. The permeability of the preform was measured following the procedure described in [12] and found to be $2.40 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$. The experimental result of the shape of the flow front at different times injected at a single gate is illustrated in Figure 7. Numerical predictions are also compared with the experimental observations. Close agreement was found between the numerical prediction and the experimental results. The contour plots in the numerical simulation is the distribution of pressure at each time step. Progressive injection has been performed in the designed sequence. The process conditions were identical to those in the single gate injection. Figure 8 shows the experimental and numerical results for this case. Close agreement was also found between the two results. The volumetric filled fraction of the mold cavity during mold filling has been compared for the single and multiple gate injections. As was predicted, Figure 9 shows that multiple gates reduce the mold filling time by a big margin of 39% compared to the case of single gate injection. In order to emphasize the effectiveness of the multi-port injection, another numerical result was shown for a comparison. The additional numerical result was obtained for the case of single port injection when the injection pressure is doubled to 200kPa. The comparison shows that the mold filling time for single gate injection may still be longer than multi-gate injection even if the injection pressure is doubled.

FURTHER NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this example, the method of progressive opening of multiple injection gates has been applied to a realistic three dimensional geometry. The geometry considered was the front panel of a tourist bus, the dimensions of which have been taken from the actual values of an existing model. The width of the panel is 2844mm, and the height is 670mm at the front face. The depth of the panel was 468mm. The geometry and mesh system are shown in Figure 10a. The striped plot is for the flow front location at an equal time interval of 40s. The result from single gate injection is shown in Figure 10b. The injection has been performed at a point on the center line of the panel. The time interval for each stripe is 40s. The mold filling time was estimated to be 2,390s. With a multi-gate system, the injection has been performed starting at the same point as the single gate injection. Four more injection gates, prepared at some designed points optimized through a number of numerical simulations, were progressively opened as the resin flow advances, and the flow front velocity is restored. Figure 10c illustrates the location of flow fronts at an equal interval time of 40s. The restoration of the flow front velocity at the opening of new gates can be clearly seen from the figure. The processing parameters were identical to the case of single gate injection. The total mold filling time was reduced down to 940s by multi-gate injection, and hence the reduction in filling time was as much as 60%.

CONCLUSION

A numerical code was developed to simulate resin transfer mold filling process with progressive opening of multiple injection ports. The resin flow can be predicted using the developed code considering heat transfer and resin cure reaction. To verify the validity of the numerical code, experiments were performed, showing a close agreement with the numerical prediction. The effectiveness of multi-gate injection was confirmed through numerical and experimental observations. The computer code developed in this study can be applied with reasonable accuracy in predicting the resin flow and related process variables and thus aids in the design of the mold and process conditions.

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Figure 1. Resin transfer molding (RTM) process

Figure 2. Progressive opening in comparison with simultaneous opening of multiple injection gates

Figure 3. Resin flow velocities in single port injection and multiple ports injection

Figure 4. Experimental Apparatus

Figure 5. Flow sensor to detect the arrival of the resin front

Figure 6. Mold Geometry and Locations of Injection and Ventilation Ports

Figure 7. Experimental observation (left) and numerical prediction (right) of resin flow by single point injection

Figure 8. Experimental observation (left) and numerical prediction (right) of resin flow by progressively opened multiple injection gates

Figure 9. Volumetric filled fractions from different injection strategies as functions of time

Figure 10. Mold filling simulation of a front panel of a tourist bus with single and multiple injection ports